

Potential effects of bottom trawling on organic carbon stocks in Denmark's marine sediments.

A Scientific Briefing

Data Sheet

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Title: Potential effects of bottom trawling on organic carbon stocks in Denmark's marine sediments.

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1. Background

Marine sediments are recognised as important habitats for the capture and long-term storage of organic carbon (OC). Globally, it is estimated that within surficial sediments $87,000 \pm 43,000$ Mt is held within the top 5 cm (Lee *et al.*, 2019), with potentially up to 3,117,000 Mt OC held within the top 1 m (Atwood *et al.*, 2020). Each year these stores grow by an estimated 156 Mt OC through the accumulation and burial of OC at the seabed (Bernier, 1982; Hedges and Keil, 1995; Smith *et al.*, 2015). However, anthropogenic pressures which increasingly disturb the seabed have the potential to not only disrupt benthic ecosystems but may also affect the OC stored within these sediments and could release carbon dioxide (CO₂) (Duplisea *et al.*, 2001), further contributing to global anthropogenic GHG emissions.

Of the anthropogenic activities that take place on the seabed, bottom trawling is recognised as the most frequent and widespread with up to 4.9 million km² of the seafloor being impacted annually (Kaiser *et al.*, 2006; Rijnsdorp *et al.*, 2016; Eigaard *et al.*, 2017; Kenny *et al.*, 2018; Sala *et al.*, 2021). During bottom contact fishing (i.e., bottom trawling) sediments are resuspended and this results in the exposure of buried OC to oxygen-rich overlying waters, potentially enhancing OC remineralisation processes (Arndt *et al.*, 2013), reducing the quantity of OC stored in marine sediments, and releasing CO₂ to the water column. Additionally, impacts on the seabed biome, including the reduction of flora and fauna, may also impact OC storage within marine sediments (Epstein *et al.*, 2022). Conversely, any loss of OC due to anthropogenic activity may be offset by a reduction of bioturbation, reduced respiration rates, and an increase in primary production due to a decrease in fauna and an increase in nutrient availability (Epstein *et al.*, 2022).

Unlike many of the environmental changes taking place in our oceans (oxygen availability, temperature, ocean acidification, etc.), all of which potentially impact sedimentary OC stores, bottom trawling pressures of the seabed can be monitored and managed to safeguard the most vulnerable sediment OC stores. By removing or reducing these pressures in marine protected areas (MPAs), for example, it may be possible to alleviate many of the negative impacts of fishing pressures and protect marine life and sedimentary environments with the highest OC storage potential.

This briefing is the product of a research agreement between Danmarks Naturfredningsforening (DN) and the University of St Andrews (UStA), Department of Geography and Sustainable Development, with the aim to provide an estimate of the potential effects of bottom trawling on the OC stored within Denmark's surficial marine sediments.

The focus of this briefing are the sub-tidal marine sediments within Denmark's Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZ). Additionally, the effect of bottom trawling on the sedimentary OC stocks within the MPAs that are composed of the Natura 2000 areas (N2000) and areas protected according to the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) and within the 3, 6 and 12-nautical mile boundaries will be assessed to potentially allow new recommendations to be made for the development of appropriate management and policy interventions (*Figure 1.1*). In this report the MPA network used in the assessment is based

on the network from 31st December 2021; since then additional MPAs have been designated.

Figure 1.1. The Natura 2000 Marine Protected Area (MPA) network (excluding 7 SPAs designated in 2022) and existing MPAs designated under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) within Denmark's Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ).

The briefing is broken down into three components, each focusing on one of the research questions listed below, and the briefing is organised accordingly.

Question 1: What is the quantity of the organic carbon stock in Danish marine sediments?

Approach: We quantified the OC held within the top 10 cm of sediment within Denmark's EEZ using two contrasting approaches:

- **Sediment type derived OC stock:** Using existing seabed sediment maps and freely available sediment data (e.g., grain size, OC content) the OC stock of each major sediment types within the EEZ were calculated.
- **Spatial modelled OC stock:** Utilizing freely available point data and a Kriging spatial modelling approach (Cressie, 1990) several spatial layers were produced:
 - Porosity (Φ)
 - Dry Bulk Density (kg m^{-3})
 - OC Content (%)
 - OC Storage (kg C m^{-2})

Together, these spatial layers allowed the OC held within the surficial sediments (top 10 cm) of Denmark's EEZ, maritime zones and MPAs to be calculated.

Question 2: What is the direct effect of bottom trawling on Danish marine sediments?

Approach: We mapped bottom trawling occurrence and frequency of different gear types across Denmark's EEZ using Vessel Monitoring System (VMS) data compiled between 2015 -2018 for bottom contact fisheries. This assessment of trawling impact includes a comparison of the trawling pressure in the different sediment types, nautical zones (e.g., 3-, 6- and 12-mile limit) and MPA network

Question 3: What is the potential effect of bottom trawling on Danish sedimentary organic carbon stocks?

Approach: We estimated the labile (reactive) fraction of the sedimentary OC stock (**Q1**) using surrogate data from the North Sea to quantify the OC most at risk from anthropogenic disturbance and combined this with the pressure assessments based on the swept area ratio (**Q2**) to calculate and map the OC at risk using a novel carbon vulnerability ranking methodology.

2. What is the quantity of the organic carbon stock in Danish marine sediments?

2.1 Methods

To answer this question, we developed two contrasting approaches based on studies conducted across the North Sea and within the United Kingdom EEZ (Diesing *et al.*, 2017; Smeaton *et al.*, 2021) to calculate the OC held within Denmark's marine sediments:

- Sediment type derived OC stock
- Spatially modelled OC stock

Data Compilation

Data were accessed from several repositories representing a range of different variables:

- Fraction Mud (F_{mud} , $<63\mu\text{m}$)
- Sediment Type (Folk Class)
- OC content (%)

However, in both the Danish EEZ and within the global sediment databases more widely, there is a general scarcity of dry bulk density data which is important for estimating OC stocks. To compensate for this lack of data, we use a simple modelling approach where we employed the more readily available F_{mud} data ($n = 751$) in conjunction with equations from Jenkins (2005) to estimate porosity (Φ)(*equation 1*) and in turn dry bulk density (*equation 2*).

$$\Phi = 0.3805 \times F_{\text{mud}} + 0.42071 \quad (\text{eq.1})$$

Both Φ and F_{mud} are reported as dimensionless fractions.

$$\text{Dry Bulk Density (kg m}^{-3}\text{)} = (1-\Phi) \times \text{Grain Density (kg m}^{-3}\text{)} \quad (\text{eq.2})$$

Following Diesing *et al.* (2017) a grain density value of $2,650 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ was used in the calculations.

Sediment type derived OC Stock

Using data freely accessed from the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS), the areal extent of the 7 sediment types defined by the Folk classification scheme (Folk, 1954; Kaskela *et al.*, 2019) were calculated from Denmark's sediment type map (*Figure 2.1*). Dry bulk density and OC content values were calculated for each sediment type from the compiled dataset (*Table 2.1*). Where OC data for a specific sediment type was not available (i.e., sandy Mud) surrogate OC values were utilised (i.e., muddy Sand). As the outcrops of rock on the seabed are not part of the active sedimentary system, zero OC values are assigned to all variables and therefore only 5 sediment types are included (*Table 2.1*).

Table 2.1. Mean physical property and OC values for the main sediment types within the Danish EEZ.

Sediment Type	Porosity (Φ)	Dry Bulk Density (kg m^{-3})	OC Content (%)
Sand	0.47 ± 0.09	1400 ± 227	1.51 ± 2.04
Coarse	0.44 ± 0.03	1488 ± 84	0.20 ± 0.20
Mixed	0.51 ± 0.10	1304 ± 273	2.40 ± 2.54
Mud	0.68 ± 0.12	837 ± 323	4.21 ± 2.31
muddy Sand	0.56 ± 0.12	1165 ± 325	2.86 ± 2.43

The area estimates, in conjunction with the dry bulk density and OC data for each sediment type, were used with equations 3–6 (below) within a Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) framework to calculate both the OC stock and storage for each of the 7 sediment classes, the sum of these OC stocks equals the quantity of OC stored in the sediments within Denmark's EEZ.

$$\text{Volume (m}^3\text{)} = \text{Area (m}^2\text{)} \times \text{Depth (m)} \quad (\text{eq.3})$$

$$\text{Mass (kg)} = \text{Volume (m}^3\text{)} \times \text{Dry Bulk Density (kg m}^{-3}\text{)} \quad (\text{eq.4})$$

$$\text{Carbon Stock (kg)} = \text{Mass (kg)} \times \text{Carbon Content (\%)} \quad (\text{eq.5})$$

$$\text{Carbon Storage (kg m}^{-2}\text{)} = \text{Carbon Stock (kg)} / \text{Area (m}^2\text{)} \quad (\text{eq.6})$$

As noted above, a MCMC framework was utilized to undertake these calculations and provided robust estimates of accompanying uncertainty in OC stocks. MCMC analysis was applied within the OpenBUGS software package (Lunn *et al.*, 2009) by taking 1,000,000 out of 10,000,000 random samples from a normal distribution of each variable (area, dry bulk density, OC content) to calculate the quantity of OC held within the sediments. The application of standard descriptive statistical techniques to the pool of generated solutions

allows the mean, median standard deviation, 5th and 95th percentiles to be calculated.

Figure 2.1. Denmark's sediments defined using the modified Folk classification scheme (Folk, 1954; Kaskela *et al.*, 2019). *Data accessed from the Geological Survey of Denmark and Greenland (GEUS).*

Spatially modelled OC stock

Simple Kriging, (Cressie, 1990) was used to model the different variables (F_{mud} and OC content) across the Danish EEZ; this approach is suited for continuous data, and Gaussian geostatistical simulations can be integrated into the mapping (Li and Heap, 2014). This approach is similar to MCMC simulations but undertaken within ArcGIS and with the added spatial component. Following this approach, the F_{mud} and OC content were spatially modelled from the available point data (*Figure 2.2*). Equations (1-6) were sequentially applied to the raster outputs from the modelling. The calculations undertaken using the Raster Calculator Tool were simulated 1,000 times for each calculation stage to ensure the accurate calculation of dry bulk density, porosity and subsequently OC stock. The summation of the values of all raster grid cells yielded the total OC of the Danish EEZ.

Figure 2.2. Location of compiled and calculated point observations in the Danish EEZ. **(A)** Fraction Mud ($n = 751$), **(B)** Dry Bulk density ($n = 751$), **(C)** Porosity ($n = 751$), **(D)** OC content ($n = 635$).

2.2 Results

Sediment type derived OC Stock

It is estimated that OC stocks for the surficial sediments (top 10 cm) of Denmark's EEZ hold a total of **332.14 ± 123.88 Mt OC**. Across the EEZ, mud deposits store the greatest quantity of OC overall, followed by muddy sands (Table 2.2). While coarser sediments (sand, coarse and mixed generally have a lower OC content than other sediment types (Table 2.1), the extensive areal coverage of these sediment types across the Danish EEZ (Figure 2.1) and their relatively high dry bulk densities (Table 2.1) result in the large quantities of OC being held with these sediment type.

Table 2.2. OC stocks and OC storage values for the different sediment types found in the Denmark's EEZ. Mainland EEZ refers to the sediments in all Danish waters, excluding Bornholm.

Sediment Type	OC Stock (Mt)	OC Storage (kg C m ⁻²)
Sand	2.00 ± 0.93	0.31 ± 0.14
Coarse	55.20 ± 37.26	4.15 ± 2.79
Mixed	49.24 ± 32.10	3.68 ± 2.39
Mud	145.89 ± 100.22	3.24 ± 2.21
muddy Sand	79.70 ± 53.55	3.97 ± 2.66
sandy Mud	0.11 ± 0.08	3.97 ± 2.66
Rock	0	0
Mainland EEZ	292.89 ± 108.43	3.11 ± 1.15
Bornholm EEZ	39 ± 15.45	3.64 ± 1.43
Denmark EEZ	332.14 ± 123.88	3.52 ± 2.38

Spatially modelled OC stock

The spatial modelling approach estimates that the sediments of Denmark's EEZ (excluding Bornholm) hold **104.68 ± 31.73 Mt OC**. This approach to estimating the sedimentary OC stocks allows the spatial distribution of the sedimentary OC to be mapped and highlights the highly heterogeneous OC storage values over much of the Danish EEZ (Figure 2.3). Notable exceptions are the distinct OC hotspots in the estuaries, fjords, and the coastal and inshore regions to Southeast of Denmark (Figure 2.3). These results highlight the importance of coastal and inshore muds within EEZ-wide C budgets (e.g., Legge *et al.*, 2020). Unfortunately, the lack of available physical property data from the seabed around Bornholm restricts our use of the spatial modelling approach to the main (western) sector of the Danish EEZ (Figure 2.3). It should be noted that the outcrops of rock on the seabed may contain fossil OC; this is not part of the active sedimentary OC pool and is therefore not considered further in this study.

Figure 2.3. Modelled seabed variables (A) porosity, (B) Dry bulk density, (C) OC content, (D) OC storage.

Sedimentary OC stock comparison

The sediment type and spatial mapping approaches used to calculate the OC stock of the surficial sediments of the Danish EEZ return significantly differing estimates. While these two approaches to calculating the surficial sediment OC stocks result in different estimates, each method carries unique advantages and disadvantages.

The first approach uses existing sediment maps and does not require the same quantity of ground-truth data to make first-order estimates of the surficial OC stock of the seabed. The drawbacks to this method are that it does not allow accurate spatial mapping, and hotspots for OC storage cannot be readily identified. Furthermore, by universally applying mean dry bulk density and OC values (*Table 2.1*) to the areal extent of each sediment type there is a high probability that the OC stocks will be overestimated (*Smeaton et al., 2021*).

The spatial modelling approach is however far more data, and potentially computationally, intensive. In certain situations, there may be insufficient data to support this approach. For the Danish EEZ, this second approach has allowed the detailed spatial mapping of OC and the identification of OC hotspots.

As the spatial modelling approach produces both spatially constrained OC stock estimates and is more conservative in its estimations, these data have been deemed the primary OC stock data to underpin this report and are used from here onwards (*Table 2.3*).

To provide a full overview of Danish sediments the OC stock for the seabed around Bornholm was calculated using the value derived from the sediment type (*Table 2.2*) and a correction obtained from a comparison of the two mapping methods. The spatial modelling methodology estimates the seabed around the main portion of the EEZ holds **104.68 ± 31.73 Mt OC**, which is 64% smaller than that calculated using the sediment type mapping approach. When this correction is applied to the OC stock from Bornholm it is estimated that the sediments hold **14.03 ± 5.52 Mt OC**.

Table 2.3. Summary of sedimentary OC stock* within Danish waters (*values calculated using sediment type). Note that the MPAs within Bornholm waters are excluded, as are the 12, 6 and 3 nautical mile values for OC in sediments from the waters around Bornholm.

Maritime Region	OC Stock (Mt)
12 Nautical Mile Limit	75.58 ± 21.73
6 Nautical Mile Limit	51.73 ± 14.53
3 Nautical Mile Limit	33.69 ± 7.73
MPAs (Natura 2000 and MSFD)	25.19 ± 3.22
Mainland EEZ	104.68 ± 31.73
Bornholm EEZ*	14.03 ± 5.52
Denmark EEZ	118.71 ± 37.25

The surficial sediments (top 10cm) within the Denmark's EEZ are estimated to hold **118.71 ± 37.25 Mt of OC**. National sedimentary OC stocks are rare with the United Kingdom (UK) being only other nation with comparable estimate. Within the UKs EEZ it is estimated that the surficial sediments (top 10cm) hold **524 ± 68 Mt of OC** (Smeaton et al., 2020). The large difference in OC stock between Denmark and the UK is driven by the areal extent of the EEZs with the UKs being more the seven times as large as Denmark's. When area normalized the sediments within the Danish EEZ store **1.13 ± 0.35 kg OC m⁻²** which compares favourably to the UK EEZ. Within the UK EEZ the sediment store between 0.770 kg OC m⁻² in the sandy continental shelf sediments and 2.19 kg OC m⁻² in the muddy OC rich sediment within fjords (Smeaton and Austin, 2019; Smeaton et al., 2020). Additionally at the regional scale the NW European shelf is estimated to hold 476 Mt of OC (Diesing et al., 2017), while the North Sea and Skagerrak are estimated to hold 230.5 ± 134.5 Mt OC (Diesing et al., 2021).

3. What is the direct effect of bottom trawling on Danish marine sediments?

3.1 Methods

We compiled Vessel Monitoring System (VMS) data for the period between 2015 - 2018 for all mobile bottom contacting (i.e., trawling) fisheries in Danish waters. Under European legislation, all vessels greater than 12 meters in length must report their fishing activity via VMS to monitor fishing activity spatially and temporally within European waters (Gerritsen and Lordan, 2011; Rouse *et al.*, 2017). By bringing together logbook and VMS datasets, the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) data centre can analyse this information to estimate the spatial and temporal distribution of bottom trawling activity and its pressure on the seabed within the OSPAR and HELCOM maritime regions. However, due to the lack of implementation of VMS on vessels under 12 meters in length, there is currently a large knowledge gap surrounding the spatial and temporal fishing patterns of (and pressures from) the inshore fishing fleet.

VMS datasets were chosen for this study instead of the alternative automatic identification systems (AIS) as VMS separates seabed swept area ratio (SAR) data by gear type, unlike AIS data which reports trawling as a singular activity with no distinction of the gear used. Additionally, due to the ability of fishers to turn off AIS tracking systems and known issues with data reporting, the VMS datasets are considered a more reliable, if incomplete, assessment of this anthropogenic pressure from bottom trawling.

Using the reported VMS data combined with log-book records, it is possible to calculate the seabed SAR following equation 7.

$$\text{SAR} = \text{Gear Width} \times \text{Vessel Speed} \times \text{Time spent Fishing} / \text{Cell Area} \quad (\text{eq.7})$$

The seabed SAR indicates the theoretical number of times a grid cell would be “swept” annually if the fishing effort were evenly distributed throughout a set grid cell area (ICES, 2020). Using the VMS data, it is possible to establish the annual average SAR across the Danish EEZ. To avoid a single year bias, the SAR of each cell has been averaged from 2015 to 2018.

To evaluate the area impacted by trawling, we combine the SAR data with the sediment type (*Figure 2.1*) and the MPA boundaries (*Figure 1.1*) to quantify the fishing effort across these different maritime zones and seabed habitats.

3.2 Results

Bottom contact fishing in the Danish EEZ

Bottom contact fishing activity measured by SAR (*Figure 3.1*) typically occurs within areas primarily to the North and West of Denmark. However, this information can be broken down further to detail the specific gear usage patterns throughout Danish waters (*Figure 3.2*) and could be further updated (and these assessments repeated or new scenarios tested) as these patterns change in the future.

Figure 3.1. Swept area ratio (SAR) across Denmark's EEZ. (A) Surface sediments (<2 cm penetration depth), (B) sub-surface sediments (> 2 cm penetration depth).

Within Denmark's EEZ, and from the available ICES data, bottom trawling activity can be grouped into one of the four main gear types: (i) otter trawls, (ii) beam trawls, (iii) bottom seines, and (iv) pelagic and seine trawls (*Figure 3.2*). All of these differ in the trawling technique used and the sediment penetration depth of the gear types.

The activity of these four gear types for vessels >12 meters is reported by ICES as VMS data. As previously noted, this data is only reported for vessels >12 meters, and it is important to acknowledge that there is therefore an underestimation of trawling occurring within Danish waters, particularly within coastal areas where vessels are typically <12 meters in length. Otter trawls are the most widely used due to their compact nature, allowing for their use across various vessel sizes. As a result, they have the broadest spatial distribution throughout the Danish EEZ (*Figure 3.2E*). Beam trawling activity occurs primarily to the West of Denmark, which is explained by it being banned in the Kattegat and the Baltic Sea (*Figure 3.2F*). Pelagic trawls and seines, and bottom seines are used across Danish waters but the active fishing time with

these gears are considerably/noticeably lower than the otter and beam trawls (Figure 3.2B and D). It should be noted that there is limited data available regarding gear penetration depth for seining gear (Eigaard *et al.*, 2016). The use of dredge gear is not recorded within the available data, however fishing with dredge gear for mussels occurs coastally and in fjords in Denmark (Gislason *et al.* 2021), and can locally have a large impact on the seafloor and ecosystem (Dolmer and Frandsen, 2002; Frandsen *et al.*, 2025)

Figure 3.2. The average fishing time (hrs) within the Danish EEZ between 2015 - 2018 for (A) All gear types, (B) Pelagic trawls and seines, (C) Bottom seines, (D) Otter trawls (E) Beam trawls.

Areas affected by mobile bottom contacting fishing

The primary focus of bottom trawling in Danish waters is focused on the muddy sands (*Figure 3.3*); within these sediments otter and beam trawls are the gear types most employed (*Figure 3.2*). Within Danish waters the greatest fishing effort occurs offshore beyond the 6 nautical mile limit (*Figure 3.3*) which is in contrast to that observed within the UK EEZ where significant bottom trawling takes place within the coastal region (< 3 nautical mile limit) (Black *et al.*, 2021). These differences are likely driven by the sediment type as a primary control; the most heavily fished sediments (muddy sand) in the Danish EEZ is found offshore (*Figure 2.1*), while these sediment types dominate the inshore areas of the UK shelf (Smeaton *et al.*, 2021).

Figure 3.3. Swept area ratio (SAR) across the different sediment types within the Danish mainland EEZ and within the different maritime zones. Box plot—dotted line: mean; solid line: median; triangles: 5th and 95th percentile.

The MPA network (Natura 2000 and MSFD) on average is impacted more by bottom trawling than the rest of the Danish EEZ (*Figure 3.3*). Yet the distribution of bottom trawling across the MPA network is uneven, with some MPAs receiving very little fishing pressure and some much more, although it is important to keep in mind that the current fisheries data most likely is an underrepresentation of the actual fishing pressure within MPAs, especially coastally, where smaller vessels, that in many cases are exempt from using an VMS, operate. This uneven distribution is showcased by the Skagens Gren og Skagerak MPA (the most northerly in Danish waters) that has, on average, the greatest fishing effort in all of Danish waters; this is largely due to the presence of large quantities of muddy sand which skews the seabed SAR values across the entire MPA network.

4. What is the potential effect of bottom trawling on Danish sedimentary organic carbon stocks?

4.1 Methods

Organic carbon reactivity

The reactivity of the OC within natural OC stores determines the role the store plays in climate regulation and, equally, determines the vulnerability of the store to disturbance both natural and anthropogenic (Goldstein *et al.*, 2020).

Natural biogeochemical (Arndt *et al.*, 2013; Larowe *et al.*, 2020) and hydrodynamic processes (Nittrouer & Wright, 1994) that govern the storage of OC across the marine sedimentary environment also drive its decomposition, so that ~90% of the OC that enters the marine sediment store is degraded (Middelburg, 2019). The reactivity of the OC (i.e., OC characteristics which determine OC remineralization potential (e.g., biodegradability) largely determines the degree of sediment OC degradation. These characteristics in-turn govern the vulnerability of the OC to remineralization, due to both natural and anthropogenic disturbance. Different mixtures of labile and refractory components determine the reactivity of the OC (Capel *et al.*, 2006). Labile organic matter (OM_L) is highly reactive and easily remineralized during transport and accumulation in marine settings (Arndt *et al.*, 2013; Keil *et al.*, 1994); recalcitrant and refractory (OM_R) is generally resistant to degradation (i.e., low reactivity) reducing the opportunity for the associated OC to be lost through remineralization. While OM_R is generally considered to be stable and therefore likely to be resilient, it must be remembered that there is a continuum of OM reactivity (Larowe *et al.*, 2020) and that there are biogeochemical processes that could drive the degradation and release of CO₂ from sediments rich in OM_R (i.e., *priming*; Bianchi, 2011).

Utilizing thermogravimetric methods, the OM in marine sediments can be grouped into two thermal fractions indicative of lability (Capel *et al.*, 2006; Smeaton and Austin, 2022). These OM fractions are thermally defined as OML (200°C–400°C) and OMR recalcitrant (400°C–650°C)

OM_L data is currently not available for the Danish EEZ therefore we used comparable sediment type data from the UK EEZ (Smeaton and Austin, 2022) as a surrogate. To assure that this data is analogous to Danish sediments we acquired five (noting one of these samples is just inside Norwegian waters) surficial sediment samples (*Figure 4.1*) from Prof. Marit-Solveig Seidenkrantz (Aarhus University) to carry out thermogravimetric analysis and calculated Denmark specific OM lability values.

The percentage OM_L data from the UK was averaged across the different sediment types. The mean values were combined with the Danish sediment

map (Figure 2.1) to create a new spatial layer. This spatial layer was merged with the map of OC content and OC storage values to produce new map layers displaying Labile OC (%) and Labile OC storage (kg C m^{-2}). Following the same approach as previously used (Section 2.1), the stock of labile OC can be estimated for the regions within Denmark's EEZ.

Figure 4.1. Location of the five sediment samples available to ground-truth the thermogravimetric analyses reported in this study.

Carbon vulnerability ranking

We evaluate the impacts of different bottom contact fishing pressures by creating a sedimentary OC vulnerability ranking (CVR) map. This CVR map details areas of the Danish EEZ seabed where surficial (top 10cm) OC stores are at the highest risk from bottom-contact fishing activity and highlight areas that would benefit from some form of management intervention to deliver OC safeguarding alongside other criteria for marine protection. The outputs presented here for Denmark's EEZ represent one of the first mapping efforts to understand the potential vulnerability of sedimentary OC from bottom trawling disturbance.

For the purposes of this briefing, we define vulnerability as a measure of the probability that the OC content of a pre-defined geographical area is likely to be damaged or disrupted by the impact of a particular hazard, in this case, bottom trawling.

A CVR value for each pixel within a raster dataset was estimated using the multi-criteria decision analysis method known as fuzzy set theory, which is a widely used modelling approach in complex systems where the information supplied to a model is vague, imprecise, or ambiguous (Kahraman and Kaya,

2010; Balezentiene *et al.*, 2013). The full methodological breakdown of the techniques used to calculate the CVR can be found in Black *et al.*, (2022).

4.2 Results

Organic carbon reactivity

The five samples of sediment (provided by Prof. Marit-Solveig Seidenkrantz) produced OC content values ranging between 1.2% to 6.1% reflecting their vicinity to the coast, with the highest value found in Aarhus Bay and the lowest in the Skagerrak. Thermogravimetric analyses (Smeaton and Austin, 2022) estimated that the OM_L content of the samples ranged between 0.83% in the Skagerrak to a maximum of 6.08% in Aarhus Bay. The OM_L values observed are comparable to those observed in the North Sea (Figure 4.2), allowing these to be used as a surrogate for Danish sediments in this study.

Figure 4.2. Labile (OM_L) versus refractory (OM_R) OM cross plot for inshore, coastal, and offshore UK Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) sediments. The radiating lines represent the carbon reactivity index (CRI) where 0 = fully reactive and 1 = non-reactive. Grey triangles represent values from the UK EEZ ($n = 885$). Yellow stars highlight the five additional samples analysed in this study.

To map the quantity of OM_L across Denmark's marine sediments the average percentage of OM_L as a function of total OM was calculated for the different

sediment types present in Danish waters (*Table 4.1*). These values were applied to the corresponding mapped sediment types (*Figure 2.1*) to create a spatial layer, and this was then combined with the OC mapping (*Figure 2.3*) to map the overall distribution of labile OC (*Figure 4.3*).

Table 4.1. Average percentage OML as a function of Total OM for the different sediment types found in Denmark’s EEZ, excluding Bornholm. Sample data and numbers of observations (n) for these sediment types are based on values from the UK EEZ.

Sediment Type	OML (%)	n
Sand	20.20 ± 6.67	166
Coarse	22.93 ± 5.09	44
Mixed	20.78 ± 6.49	35
Mud	41.06 ± 12.65	34
sandy Mud	41.93 ± 13.89	86
Muddy Sand	33.54 ± 12.37	64

Utilizing the same methodology as section 3, we estimate that the surficial (top 10 cm) sediments within the main portion of Denmark’s EEZ hold **23.20 ± 7.38 Mt** of labile OC with a further **4.21 ± 2.05 Mt** of Labile OC held within the sediments around Bornholm. The sediments within the 12 NM limit, excluding the waters around Bornholm, hold 72.1% of this labile OC, with the majority being held within the Southeast sector of the EEZ (*Figure 4.3*). Across the other maritime regions, the total quantity of labile OC decreases in line with the total OC content (*Figure 4.4*) with **11.34 ± 4.40 Mt**, **7.24 ± 2.30 Mt** and **5.53 ± 0.77 Mt** of labile OC stored within the 6 NM limit, 3NM limit and the Natura 2000 network respectively (*Figure 4.4*), excluding the additional OC held in the waters around Bornholm.

Figure 4.3. Spatial distribution of OC in the surficial (top 10 cm) sediments across the Denmark's EEZ, excluding Bornholm. **(A)** Total OC storage, **(B)** Labile OC storage. For the purposes of better illustrating the spatial heterogeneity of the data only the mainland EEZ has been displayed.

The labile OC is the most reactive of the OC pools in the marine sediments (Smeaton and Austin, 2022). Therefore, for the purpose of this briefing, we consider the labile OC to represent the fraction of the total OC most at risk of being remineralized by natural and anthropogenic seabed disturbance.

Figure 4.4. Surficial sediment OC stocks broken down into total OC and labile OC for different regions with Denmark's EEZ.

Vulnerability of sedimentary OC to bottom trawling

By bringing together the labile OC mapping (*Figure 4.3*) with the fishing pressure measured by SAR (*Figure 3.1*) we assess the potential risk to the OC held within Denmark's marine sediments. Using the CVR we can identify the areas where the loss of OC is most likely from bottom trawling activities (Smeaton and Austin, 2022). The areas of the seabed most at risk from losing sedimentary OC due to disturbance are found to the West and North of the Danish EEZ (*Figure 4.5E*).

The CVR mapping provides the first steps towards the development of potential management and policy interventions to protect the sedimentary OC from anthropogenic disturbance. The majority of sedimentary OC at risk from trawling fall outside the current MPA network (*Figure 4.5F*), this pattern is not exclusive to Denmark, for example in the UK the current MPA network also fails to align with the most at-risk sedimentary OC stores (Epstein and Roberts, 2022). Yet, the Skagens Gren og Skagerak MPA (the most northerly in Danish waters) does align with high to very high CVR values indicating a high likelihood that a fraction of the OC in these sediments will be lost due to bottom contact fishing. As this activity takes place inside an existing MPA there may be an opportunity to use existing management and policy mechanisms to strengthen the protection of the sedimentary OC in this area.

Figure 4.5. Seabed sediment organic carbon vulnerable to bottom contact fishing within the Denmark's EEZ. (A-B) Labile OC, (C-D) Swept are ratio (SAR), (E-F) Carbon vulnerability ranking. Panels B, D and F highlight the location of MPAs. For the purposes of better illustrating the spatial heterogeneity of the data only the mainland EEZ has been displayed.

5. Conclusion

This scientific briefing aimed to quantify the potential effect of bottom contact fishing on sedimentary OC held within Denmark's EEZ and generate new spatial assessment tools to support further management and conservation measures.

To achieve this aim we initially needed to quantify the amount of OC held within the surficial sediments (top 10 cm) across Denmark's EEZ. By integrating freely available data with two contrasting modelling approaches we estimated that Denmark's surficial sediments hold **118.71 ± 37.25** of OC (*Table 2.3*). To understand the fraction of the OC that may be at risk from anthropogenic bottom disturbance we utilised OC reactivity data from the wider North Sea (Smeaton and Austin, 2022). This approach allowed the quantity of labile (reactive, most at risk) OC to be determined. Within Denmark's EEZ it is estimated that there is **27.24 ± 6.89 Mt** of OC that, if disturbed, is under a high probability (and risk) of remineralization and loss. The actual amount of remineralization and the scale of the emissions of greenhouse gasses associated with these disturbances (e.g., Sala et al., 2021) remain contested in the academic literature (see, for example, Black et al., 2022). However, remineralization of the stored carbon might not only lead to emissions of greenhouse gasses, but disturbances of the stored carbon might also contribute to an enhanced local ocean acidification effect.

We brought together bottom contact fisheries data in the form of fishing time and SAR to explore the potential magnitude of seabed disturbance from trawling. Within Danish waters, otter and beam trawls are the most common gear used; the seabed West of Denmark experiences the greatest amount of fishing activity (*Figure 3.2*). When compared with the seabed sediment type, most of the bottom trawling effort takes place on the muddy sand (*Table 3.3*) with the highest sediment SAR observed in the North of the EEZ (*Figure 3.1*).

To evaluate the potential impact of trawling on the sedimentary OC stores present, we combined the newly created OC stock maps with the compiled fishing data to produce a CVR map of the entire Danish EEZ. This new map (*Figure 4.4*) highlights that the sedimentary OC stores most at risk can be found to the West and North of the EEZ, primarily in muddy sands. With the exception of the Skagens Gren og Skagerak MPA (the most northerly in Danish waters) the OC stores most at risk from bottom trawling do not align with the current MPAs (*Figure 4.5*).

Going forward, there is a need for surficial and down-core sediment samples to be collected across Denmark's EEZ to produce Denmark-specific dry bulk density and OC content data which can be used to ground-truth and improve the mapping in this briefing. This is particularly relevant for the Danish EEZ around Bornholm, where there is potential for a very large stock of vulnerable sedimentary OC, but very little constraining data at present. Essential to understanding the impact of seabed disturbance on sedimentary OC is the quantifying of the reactivity of the OC; we would therefore advocate that OM lability measurement (e.g., Thermogravimetric analysis; Smeaton and Austin, 2022) is undertaken on all new samples. Secondly, our spatial understanding of trawling within coastal areas by

vessels <12m in length needs to be improved to understand the fishing industry's true impact on seabed sediment OC storage, as highlighted by the apparent lack of use of dredge gear in Danish waters in the available data, which is not accurate, since mussel dredging does occur in Denmark Coastal sediments are the most OC rich and potentially most vulnerable to disturbance; it is therefore essential that the impact of any bottom contact fishing activity in these areas is better understood, monitored, and eventually managed to protect the most vulnerable stores of marine sediment OC. However, even with better and more expansive data, understanding the impact of bottom trawling on sedimentary OC stores and the overall negative impact of these activities on climate change will remain challenging. Despite these scientific challenges, we highlight that there is a clear and growing imperative to improve the quantification of the effects of bottom trawling on the globally significant storage potential of OC in marine sediments.

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